

Challenges Chemistry teachers face in implementing the new Namibia Senior Secondary Certificate Ordinary level Chemistry Curriculum during the COVID-19 National Lockdown in Otjozondjupa Region

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Abstract: *The COVID-19 pandemic forced schools around the world to cancel face to face classes and mandated teachers to adopt remote teaching. This study aimed to investigate the Challenges Grade 10 and 11 Chemistry teachers in Otjozondjupa Region of Namibia face during the remote implementation of the Chemistry curriculum. The study adopted an explanatory sequential mixed methods approach, comprising of two phases. In the first phase, questionnaires were used to gather quantitative data from all (32) Grade 10 and 11 Chemistry teachers in the region. In the second phase, semi-structured interviews were used to collect qualitative data from 12 teachers purposively selected from the original sample. The findings revealed that Chemistry teachers utilised multiple strategies to provide learners with inclusive education through remote teaching and learning. However, they experienced difficulties such as inadequate resources and a lack of technological competency to effectively teach Chemistry remotely. Other challenges included: difficulties accessing and staying in contact with learners; inability to engage learners in virtual lessons due to a lack of electronic devices and internet connectivity particularly on the learners' side; nonfulfillment of practical work and difficulty in assessing learners during remote teaching. In consideration of the findings, several recommendations were made, including the recommendation that the national government should provide schools with adequate technological facilities and furnish unequipped science laboratories, and Chemistry teachers should be offered pedagogical training programmes to equip them with e-learning teaching competencies.*

Key words: *Chemistry curriculum, Curriculum implementation, COVID-19 pandemic, Remote teaching, National Lockdown*

I. Introduction and Background

The third reform for basic education in Namibia began in 2012, as per the recommendation of the 2011 National Education Conference (Ministry of Education, Arts and Culture, n.d.-b) and its implementation then commenced in 2015 with the junior primary phase, targeted for a full implementation to take place by the year 2021 in Grade 12 (Ministry of Education, Arts and Culture, 2015). Significant change noted in the science curriculum is the replacement of Physical Science by Chemistry and Physics as two distinct subjects in Grades 10 and 11. Thus, as of 2019 the subject of Chemistry for NSSCO has been implemented for the first time in Namibian secondary schools offered as a two-year course, with its first implementation in Grade 10 having taken place in 2019 and in Grade 11 in 2020 (Ministry of Education Arts and Culture, n.d.-a). The National Curriculum for Basic Education (NCBE) in Namibia, which is the broad curriculum, states that Science is one of the driving forces

behind the society's and the world's transformation. It further suggests that science is one of the key learning areas in the NCBE as it "contributes to the foundation of a knowledge-based society by empowering learners with scientific knowledge, skills and attitudes to formulate hypotheses and investigations, observe, make deductions and understand the physical world in a rational, scientific way" (Ministry of Education, Arts and Culture, 2018, p. 13). Hence, there is a need for learners to advance into scientific literate citizens (Ministry of Education, 2010). The relevance of Chemistry education in general education has been recognized on a global scale, making it one of the most important disciplines in the school curriculum (Achimugu, 2016). According to Muse et al. (2018) "the ultimate goal of studying Chemistry is to enhance people's understanding of the composition, structure, properties and changes of matter while under varied conditions". Chemistry is also a requirement for admission to scientific careers and helps to ensure continuous availability of students who take important occupations such as engineering, pharmacy, medicine, dentistry, food science, environmental education, etc. (Ikechukwu, 2011; Njagi & Silas, 2015). It is therefore crucial for any country that wants to be among the developed nations to take the teaching and learning of Chemistry seriously (Federal Republic Of Nigeria, 2004). It can therefore be asserted that it is critical that the subject of Chemistry be properly implemented to all learners taking it (Edomwonyi-Oto & Aava, 2011).

On March 11, 2020 the World Health Organization declared a global pandemic of COVID-19 (Corona Virus Disease 2019) which rapidly became a massive international concern (Wang et al., 2020; World Health Organization (WHO), 2020). In Namibia, the first COVID-19 confirmed cases were reported on March 13, 2020. Four days later, a State of Emergency was declared in the country, on account of the occurrence of Coronavirus disease (Republic of Namibia, 2020). As a response to this global pandemic, Namibia, like other countries around the world dealing with the COVID-19 crisis, introduced intensive measures to limit the spreading of the disease and its effects. One of the restrictive measures introduced in the country was a total national lockdown, which caused unexpected disruptions to different sectors. In education, the major impact of COVID-19 was the temporally closure of schools across the country as of 17th March 2020 (MoEAC, 2020). The government's decision to ultimately close schools was a positive move to protect learners and teachers from possible risks of contracting COVID-19 because a school environment is where large numbers of learners meet, and this makes it a risky place where the diseases can spread quickly (Sintema, 2020). However, the move to close schools resulted in unprecedented changes to education as face-to-face teaching and learning immediately came to a halt. In the light of the aforementioned circumstances, the Ministry of Education, Arts and Culture called for an implementation of remote teaching and learning through e-learning so that learners continued to receive education from home until a point where schools could resume (MoEAC, 2020).

II. Statement of the Problem

In an effort to salvage the educational academic year for 2020 amid COVID-19 pandemic, two weeks into the national lockdown, the government through MoEAC (2020) called for all teachers in Namibian schools to implement and facilitate online learning through technological devices such as laptops, tablets and smart phones. This was necessitated to enable teaching and learning to continue until a point where teachers and learners could resume physical contact. Hence, teachers had to unexpectedly embrace a new mode of teaching to provide education to the learners during the lockdown. However, according to the Teachers Union of Namibia (2020) most teachers did not have prior experience or training in online teaching and learning. This implies that most Chemistry teachers did not have the capacity and necessary skills to implement online learning effectively during the lockdown. Gokmenoglu and Clark (2015) stress that teachers are tasked and entrusted to implement a curriculum successfully, but their voices, challenges and personal experiences in curriculum implementation are often not adequately studied. It is against this background that this study was conducted to give Chemistry teachers, as curriculum implementers, opportunity to voice their challenges and experiences as they implement the NSSCO Chemistry curriculum during the COVID-19 pandemic national lockdown.

Research questions

The study sought to answer the following research questions:

1. What are the challenges experienced by Chemistry teachers in the implementation of the new NSSCO Chemistry curriculum in Otjozondjupa Region during the COVID-19 national lockdown?
2. What are the views of Chemistry teachers on the implementation of the new NSSCO Chemistry curriculum in Otjozondjupa Region during the COVID-19 national lockdown?
3. How can the Chemistry teachers effectively implement the new NSSCO Chemistry curriculum in Otjozondjupa Region during the COVID-19 national lockdown?

Significance of the study

The findings of the study may provide policy makers and those responsible for monitoring the implementation of the new NSSCO Chemistry curriculum with insight into the implementation of the curriculum during the COVID-19 national crisis and how the Chemistry teachers in Otjozondjupa Region coped with facilitating remote teaching. The study can also provide information on how Chemistry teachers can be supported in implementing the Chemistry curriculum particularly, during crises such as the COVID-19 pandemic. The study can assist teacher training institutions on best practices for future Chemistry teachers by aligning programmes with the ever-changing trends in teaching practices, with a focus on online learning. The study may also enable Chemistry teachers in Otjozondjupa Region to reflect on their own experiences of implementing the Chemistry curriculum remotely which can allow them to re-evaluate their practices. In turn this will empower them to build their capacity in remote and online learning and teaching.

Theoretical framework

The study is informed by the Theory of Curriculum Implementation (Rogan & Grayson, 2003), which is underpinned by three major interrelating constructs: profile of implementation, capacity to support innovation and support from outside agencies. The profile of implementation expresses the types and extent to which the ideals of a curriculum are put into practice (Tawana, 2009). The construct and capacity to support innovation is concerned with factors found within a school itself that can support or hinder the implementation process of an innovation. In this regard, the emphasis is on Chemistry teachers' educational backgrounds, their experiences of teaching a science subject virtually and how they coped during the COVID-19 crisis, the physical resources available such as technology facilities, and the challenges they faced. The third construct, which is support from outside agencies, refers to support given by organisations outside the school. Examples of such organisations are advisory departments, teachers' unions, and non-governmental organisations. The theory of curriculum implementation directed the identification of the data relevant to the research problem. In addition, it provided a theoretical lens through which the findings of the study were interpreted.

III. Literature review

The concept of Chemistry curriculum implementation

The implementation of the Chemistry curriculum refers to putting the prescribed syllabus into practice. According to Mwangi (2016), Chemistry like other science subjects, has both theoretical and practical components that complement each other during the teaching and learning processes. The theoretical aspects of the subject can be mastered effectively through traditional methods, however, experiments are required to study the practical content. Okono (2015) mention that the teaching of Chemistry through using experimentation pedagogical strategies contributes to effective teacher instruction and increases mastery of concepts by the learners. This is why, according to Kaping ' Ei and Kimeli (2014), Chemistry teachers are urged to expose learners to more experiments in the subject to achieve satisfactory performance. One advantage of experiments

is that they have been shown to help learners develop their scientific process capabilities (Kapping ' Ei & Kimeli, 2014).

Effects of COVID-19 on curriculum implementation

As a result of COVID-19, schools across the world were forced to close, causing an increased reliance on alternative modes of lesson delivery as a way to continue with teaching and learning (Goldschmidt, 2020). The effects of COVID-19 included disruption of curriculum scheduling, and in some cases, removal of some subject content for the academic year. Examinations were postponed in some countries, in some, they were cancelled and in others, they were replaced by continuous assessment (United Nations, 2020). Di Pietro et al. (2020) noted that the learning process was negatively impacted by school closure due to less time spent learning, stress symptoms in children as a result of being confined at home, and by a lack of motivation.

The failure by many schools to successfully implement curriculum during the pandemic has been exacerbated by unequal access to internet connections and an uneven distribution of learning resources, particularly for low-income and vulnerable populations (Rieble-Aubourg & Viteri, 2020). UNESCO (2020a) recommends that governments prioritize education continuity and contact for learners who have difficulty connecting to the internet and live in socioeconomic conditions that do not support distance learning processes. It is also essential for educational authorities to develop protocols for continuing education when schools reopen following the COVID-19 pandemic, and these protocols must take into account the disparities that widened during the crisis (UNESCO, 2020b).

Challenges teachers face when engaging in remote teaching

As teachers ventured into remote teaching, there was a shortfall especially in developing countries which can largely be attributed to the digital divide, with the disadvantaged having limited access to basic household services such as electricity, a lack of technology infrastructure and low level of digital literacy among both learners and teachers (UNESCO, 2020b). According to Aldarayseh (2020), challenges teachers experience in teaching science subjects online include, the absence of hands-on activities, fostering interaction in online classroom and managing learners' behaviour. Additionally, Mukhtar et al. (2020) in their studies on online learning during COVID-19 pandemic found that because of a lack of immediate feedback, teachers were unable to assess learners' levels of understanding during online lecturing.

The challenges teachers faced went beyond pedagogical and infrastructural issues. As Cachon-Zagalaz et al. (2020) state, the pandemic not only affected learners' mental health, but teachers also experienced increased stress levels since the crisis began. Studies have reported that, teachers experienced a great deal of stress during the lockdown as a result of having to make a swift shift to online teaching (Besser et al., 2022). Ng (2007) points out that as a result of increased workload associated with teaching from home, teachers were under a great deal of stress, frequently accompanied by symptoms of depression, anxiety, and sleep disturbance. Other studies have indicated that working from home using technological tools creates feelings of anxiety, exhaustion, tension, and lowered job satisfaction (Cuervo & Acquaro, 2018).

Education sector in Namibia during the COVID-19 pandemic

Nashilongo (2020) stated that when assessing the challenges of online learning during COVID-19, it is essential to present the state of technological advancement and the issue of internet connectivity across the country. A circular released by the Ministry of Education, Arts and Culture on how to deal with schooling during COVID-19; indicated that telecommunication infrastructure was the biggest challenge, when considering that 32% of the schools (614) in the Namibia did not have access to telecommunications and the internet (Nashilongo, 2020). In addition, Basilaia and Kvavadze (2020) observed that most schools in Namibia were unprepared for the implementation of nationwide online learning due to poor technology.

On the same note, Boer and Asino (2022) described insights teachers provided concerning online teaching in Namibia during the COVID-19 pandemic. Some teachers stated that online teaching highlighted the inequality to education among learners because not all learners had access to the learning content due to a lack of

technology tools and lack of internet connection. They also revealed that the availability of digital resources for teachers and learners defined what teachers were able to do, hence most teachers could not comply with the directive from the Ministry of Education, Arts and Culture to apply online learning and thus had to find other ways of conducting teaching through the distance approach.

IV. Methodology

Research design

This study followed an explanatory sequential mixed methods approach whereby quantitative data were first collected followed by the collection of qualitative data. Hence the study consisted of two separate phases. This approach permitted the participants to describe the challenges they faced in implementing the new NSSCO Chemistry curriculum during the COVID-19 national lockdown. The purpose of using mixed methods in this study was complementarity, in which findings from qualitative data were used to explore and enhance findings from quantitative data (Combs & Onwuegbuzie, 2010).

Sampling

Purposive sampling was adopted to select all Grade 10 and 11 Chemistry teachers in Otjozondjupa Region to take part in the first phase of the study. Thereafter, a sample of 12 teacher was purposively drawn from the original sample to take part in the second phase.

Data Collection

Data were collected using questionnaires and semi-structured interviews. Questionnaires were used to gather quantitative data in the first phase of the study, from all (32) Grade 10 and 11 Chemistry teachers in Otjozondjupa region. In the second phase, semi-structured interviews were used to collect qualitative data from the 12 teachers who were purposively selected from the original sample.

Data analysis

The quantitative data collected from the questionnaire were analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequencies and percentages, and presented in tables. For qualitative data, thematic analysis was used and the generated data were categorised in themes and sub-themes that emerged.

Findings

The findings from the analysis of the questionnaire and interviews were integrated. The interviews explained some of the findings which emerged from the questionnaire analysis. The data is presented according to the main themes generated from the research questions.

Theme 1: Challenges Chemistry teachers experienced in implementing the new NSSCO Chemistry curriculum during the COVID-19 national lockdown

Table 1 shows teachers' responses on the statements that required them to indicate their levels of agreement regarding the challenges experienced in the implementation of the new NSSCO Chemistry curriculum. A five-point Likert scale was used, using Strongly Disagree (SD), Disagree (D), Undecided (U), Agree (A), and Strongly Agree (SA).

Table 1
Challenges Chemistry teachers experienced when implementing the new NSSCO Chemistry curriculum during the COVID-19 national lockdown

Statements	SD	D	U	A	SA	Total
Chemistry teachers were not prepared to implement the new NSSCO Chemistry curriculum virtually.	1	3	3	14	7	28
Chemistry teachers lacked skills in utilizing technological devices in remote teaching.	1	4	4	13	6	28
Chemistry teachers felt overwhelmed with work in implementing the new NSSCO Chemistry curriculum virtually.	1	3	2	17	5	28
There was a lack of technological devices and internet connectivity for the teachers.	1	3	4	16	4	28
There was a lack of technological devices and internet connectivity for the learners.	2	4	2	17	3	28
Every learner has equal cognition to receive virtual teaching	6	16	3	2	1	28
The Chemistry teachers lacked the competencies in fostering interaction with the learners during remote teaching.	4	7	2	10	5	28
A lack of hands-on activities and experiments hindered effective teaching and learning of Chemistry during the lockdown.	2	3	2	15	6	28

From Table 1, the results indicate that in total, 21 (75%) of the teachers agreed that they were not prepared for the virtual implementation of the Chemistry curriculum, four (14%) disagreed while, three (11%) were undecided. In investigating if teachers lacked the skills to utilize technological devices in remote teaching, 19 (68%) teachers agreed to the statement, five (18%) disagreed and four (14%) of the teachers were undecided. Furthermore, 20 (71%) of the teachers indicated that they lacked technology devices and internet connectivity, four (14%) disagreed while four (14%) were undecided. On the statement if every learner had equal recognition to receive virtual teaching, 22 (79%) disagreed, three (11%) agreed while three (1%) were undecided. Furthermore, 15 (54%) of the teachers agreed that teachers lacked the competencies in fostering interaction with the learners during remote teaching, 11 (39%) disagreed while 2 (7%) were undecided. Lastly, the results in Table 1 show that 21 (75%) of the Chemistry teachers agreed that a lack of hands on activities and experiments hindered effective teaching and learning, five (18%) of the teachers disagreed while two (7%) were undecided.

In the interviews, teachers elaborated on the challenges they experienced. They voiced challenges such as a lack of technological skills, resources deficiency (textbooks and technological tools) and digital divide among learners. All these challenges hindered the teaching and learning process during the lockdown. The following excerpts from the teacher interviews highlight the aforementioned difficulties teachers faced:

Teacher 2: *I did not feel empowered nor equipped with the resources or skills to effectively teach Chemistry via remote teaching. I also didn't know how to design e-learning materials. I needed some training on how to go about the whole process...*

Teacher 8: *The challenges I faced is that I did not have the IT resources required to teach Chemistry remotely as it was expected from me. Also, most of my learners did not have smartphones or data for us to communicate and for me to send them the learning contents. On top of that, the school does not have textbooks for the learners...*

Teacher 22: *I experienced a lack of resources amongst other things, particularly the teaching and learning aids. Lack of textbooks has always been an issue too... unequal opportunity to learning as learners from disadvantages backgrounds did not have smartphones or laptops or suitable learning environments at home. This whole thing was really challenging.*

Another challenge teachers mentioned is that it was difficult to reach all the learners during remote teaching. This is revealed in the following responses:

Teacher 12: *I encountered problems such as difficulty getting in contact with my learners during the distance learning process. This made it difficult for me to send my learners the learning contents and to even check on them.*

Teacher 16: *I was not able to reach all the learners during the lockdown. The only way I could communicate with my learners was through the WhatsApp groups that I created however some learners lacked the devices for that, and such learners were left out.*

Another highlighted major challenge experienced was the absence of practical work during remote teaching as the following teachers narrated:

Teacher 8: *It was difficult to cover the practical components of the subjects as learners were not physically present in the classroom. What I did was that I left out the practical parts of the topics and only came to cover them after face to face classes resumed.*

Teacher 20: *Doing practical work was impossible because we could not meet face to face. Our science laboratory is not even equipped for me to even do and use virtual laboratories. I put my thrust on using pictures, sketches and drawing with explanations, which I sent to the learners.*

Theme 2: Views of the Chemistry teachers on the implementation of the new NSSCO Chemistry curriculum during the COVID-19 national lockdown

Chemistry teachers were asked to give their views regarding how they felt about the implementation of the new NSSCO Chemistry curriculum during the lockdown. Yes or No answers were requested from participants and the findings are presented in Table 2.

Table 2
Views of Chemistry teachers on the implementation of the new NSSCO Chemistry curriculum during the COVID-19 national lockdown

Statements	Yes	No	Total
The implementation of the Chemistry curriculum during lockdown has assisted in improving learners' learning.	4	24	28
I felt insecure about implementing the Chemistry curriculum through remote teaching.	22	6	28
I think parents assisted their children with learning during remote teaching	6	22	28
School management supported and virtually monitored remote teaching and learning during the lockdown	13	15	28
The Regional Office provided Chemistry teachers with clear guidance and support regarding remote teaching of Chemistry	16	12	28
The Regional Office virtually monitored the implementation of the new NSSCO Chemistry curriculum during the lockdown	12	16	28

Table 2 shows that 24 (86%) teachers did not think that the implementation of Chemistry during the lockdown has assisted in improving learners' learning and only four (14%) said it did. Furthermore, 22 (79%) of the teachers have indicated that they felt insecure about implementing the Chemistry curriculum remotely while six (21%) said they felt secured. On the statement if teachers thought that parents assisted their children with learning during remote teaching, only six (21%) said yes and the majority, 22 (79%) indicated no. When asked if the school management supported and virtually monitored remote teaching and learning during the lockdown, 13 (46%) of the teachers indicated yes while 15 (54%) said no. On whether the Regional Office provided teachers with clear guidance and support regarding remote teaching of Chemistry, 16 (57%) said yes while 12 (43%) indicated no. Lastly, teachers were asked if the Regional Office virtually monitored the implementation of the new NSSCO Chemistry curriculum and 11 (39%) teachers said yes while 17 (61%) said no.

In both the questionnaires and interviews, majority of the teachers were of the opinion that the implementation of the Chemistry curriculum during the lockdown did not help in improving learners learning. This is described in the following excerpts:

Teacher 4: Learners were not familiar with the distance mode and this hindered the teaching and learning process... Also, a lot of learners did not have WhatsApp which I used for communication purposes and also through which I give explanations to the contents. Such learners relied on the notes in the booklets alone and most of them failed to master the contents on their own. I literally had to start over when school reopened.

Teacher 13: Majority of learners performed poorly in the activities they completed during remote teaching and learning, which to me is an indication that not much learning took place. Some did not even attempt to do the activities. I think this happened because most of the learners learn better when given face to face explanations. In general, remote teaching did not accommodate all learners at all.

Furthermore, the teachers cited being insecure when they taught Chemistry remotely. This is because they felt unprepared in terms of the competencies and resources. Two of the teachers narrated:

Teacher 4: I felt anxious plus I had some fear in me about remote teaching. I believed that if only we had the resources and the skills to integrate technology in our teaching before the lockdown, then some of us wouldn't have felt powerless.

Teacher 16: I was not prepared for this and so I felt unsure about my abilities. The lack of resources made the situation worse.

Regarding the support rendered from the school management and Regional Office, most participants commented the support received from the school management in the interviews. However, on the support rendered to them by the Regional Office, the quantitative and qualitative data contradicted each other. In the questionnaires, most teachers indicated that they received helpful support and guidance but in the interviews, they gave opposite responses. The findings also implies that there was a lack of monitoring of the curriculum implementation. Following are two selected expressions from the teachers' interviews:

Teacher 2: The school management supported me by giving me ideas on how better I could support and keep my learners engaged in learning from home. The regional office provided me with policies, encouragement, and motivation to face the situation. I appreciate the support from both parties, but I feel that the regional office was supposed to do more in assisting, guiding us and monitoring how we were coping and implementing the curriculum.

Teacher 12: My head of department collaboratively worked with me and other teachers on how to better approach remote teaching throughout... On the support from the Regional Office, they send me some directives and that's mainly it. The management at our school tried to do more for us compared to the advisory department.

Theme 3: Strategies to help the implementation of the new NSSCO Chemistry curriculum during the COVID-19 national lockdown

Teachers suggested the following strategies to help improve the implementation of the Chemistry curriculum during remote teaching as shown in Table 3.

Table 3
Strategies to help improve the implementation of the NSSCO Chemistry curriculum during the COVID-19 national lockdown

Teacher 2	The Ministry of Education, Arts and Culture should compile teaching and learning materials to be distributed to all teachers and learners. It should also provide online workshops for teachers on how to conduct online teaching on assessment of learners during remote teaching.
Teacher 4	Increase support for teachers from school management and the education ministry. Government should increase internet penetration in schools and in communities. The schools should be equipped with adequate resources to conduct remote teaching effectively, this also include a textbook for each learner.
Teacher 6	Increase government support in training teachers and providing the necessary resources to enable efficient remote teaching. Most importantly, the use of IT in teaching Chemistry should be emphasized and so teachers should be trained on it. Teachers must be provided with guidelines regarding practical work during remote teaching.
Teacher 8	Parents should ensure that there is a conducive environment for children to learn at home. Government should help less privileged learners with gadgets for remote learning.
Teacher 10	Increased regional support for teachers. Chemistry teachers should be provided with clear remote learning guidelines, especially on the practical parts of the subject and also on assessing learners remotely
Teacher 12	The ministry should ensure that the teachers have the necessary tools and skills to practice remote teaching and that they have sufficient knowledge to use technological tools and administer classes online or remotely. The teacher training institution should also train teachers during their studies on how to integrate the use of IT in their lessons
Teacher 13	Chemistry teachers should be provided with training on how to use information and technology tools more in their teaching and also on how to assess learners' progress during remote learning.
Teacher 15	The ministry should compile teaching materials and assessment activities for remote teaching that should be provided to all Chemistry teachers so that quality work is not compromised. The ministry should also train teachers on remote teaching as majority of teachers lack the necessary skills on it and this added to teachers' stress. Schools should be equipped with enough resources as well
Teacher 16	The ministry should ensure that schools are in possession of the resources needed.
Teacher 20	Teachers require training on how to assess students during remote teaching, as well as on the use of information and technology tools in teaching
Teacher 22	Teachers must be given clear guidelines on how to go about remote teaching and the ways to effectively carryout out Chemistry classes, especially on how to cover the parts of experiments in Chemistry.
Teacher 29	Parents must be actively involved by continuously encouraging their children to continue learning, keep in touch with teachers and agree on ways which they can help improve the learning experiences of the learners

V. Conclusion

The study found that most teachers reported a lack of resources, particularly the textbooks and the digital devices (laptops, smartphones, and tablets) required to conduct e-learning during the lockdown. Compounding this was a lack of internet access faced by most learners and some teachers during remote teaching and learning. The shortage of resources made the implementation of the Chemistry curriculum a difficult task for the teachers. Teachers and learners lacked digital competencies for utilizing technological tools in teaching and learning. The study further found that it was difficult for teachers to reach the learners, teachers' difficulty in explaining complex concepts of Chemistry to learners and the teachers' inability to conduct practical work. Other challenges that teachers encountered included: Lack of learner accountability; learners were handing in their assessment activities past the due dates or not handing them in at all; unequal opportunity in education for learners in terms of digital divide; and lack of monitoring the implementation of the curriculum.

In conclusion, the study revealed that Otjzondjupa Region is lacking regarding remote teaching and learning at secondary schools. The factors outlined in the study that acted as barriers to effective remote teaching were too immense to conduct remote teaching successfully. Hence, there is high likelihood that this has resulted in learning gaps among learners.

Recommendations

In light of the findings of the study, the following recommendations are made:

- The Ministry of Education, Arts and Culture should avail funds so that the resource deficit in schools is filled, and ensure that all schools have the requisite materials to reduce learning disparities within the region. It should also provide pedagogical training programme to Chemistry teachers on the usage of technology in the online situation for the purpose of improving their digital skills as well as provide training on the best approaches to remote teaching. Additionally, the Ministry of Education should provide teachers with clear guidance on how to cover the practical aspects of Chemistry instruction and how they should administer assessment to monitor learners' progress during the remote learning.
- Advisory teachers should put effective monitoring mechanisms in place and also give Chemistry teachers full support in the implementation journey of the curriculum during distance teaching. This will enable them to determine if teachers are effective and subsequently assist them where they may be lacking.
- Chemistry teachers should take the ownership of empowering themselves with digital competencies in technology by participating in professional development programme in technology pedagogical knowledge. This will equip them with digital skills to use technology in education (teaching) so they can be better prepared for future remote teaching needs, or simply for the purpose of integrating technology to support their everyday teaching practices.
- Similar research could be conducted focusing on learners and parents as that will give them voices to express the challenges they faced and how to create effective learning environments during distance teaching and learning.

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